

Enlightening Catalytic Mechanism of Ceriporiopsis Subvermispora (CsFDH) With Site Directed Mutagenesis

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Formate dehydrogenases (FDHs) are a set of enzymes that catalyze the oxidation of formate to carbon dioxide and concomitant reduction of NAD⁺ to NADH, as well as the corresponding reverse reactions. NAD⁺-dependent formate dehydrogenase (FDH) is a high-value-added enzyme due to its usage to produce NAD(P)H coenzyme required by oxidoreductases and very limited activity against CO₂.

Although these enzymes have conserved amino acids positions forming catalytic site, they have almost different kinetic rates for the same substrate. FDH of *Ceriporiopsis subvermispora* (CsFDH, BAF98206.1) has shown lowest activity in the formate oxidation reaction compared to FDH of *Ancylobacter aquaticus* KNK607M (AaFDH, BAC65346.1), *Moraxella* sp. C-1 (MsFDH, CAA73696.1), *Paracoccus* sp. 12-A (PsFDH, BAB64941.1), *Thiobacillus* sp. KNK 65MA (TsFDH, BAC92737.1) and CbFDH (CAA09466.2).

Therefore, the most promising *Ceriporiopsis subvermispora* (CsFDH) could be a good candidate FDH to study catalytic mechanism for FDHs.

To enlighten catalytic site of CsFDH, it was aligned with well-known FDHs and non-aligned three positions were selected for mutation based on their relative proximity to the active site. Asparagine by Phenylalanine at position 312 (AsnCs312Phe), Valine by Proline at position 313 (ValCs313Pro), and Valine by Threonine at position 331 (ValCs331) were tested with site directed mutagenesis method.

The obtained experimental results showed that the selected positions contribute to form active site pocket. Computational molecular modelling will give idea about possible reasons of changing activity of CsFDH after mutations.

Keywords: *Ceriporiopsis subvermispora* (CsFDH), Catalytic site, Site directed mutagenesis, Computational molecular modelling.